

"SHAHRISABZ STATE PEDAGOGICAL INSTITUTE"

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7989805>

Abstract. *In this article, you can familiarize yourself with the Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute and get complete information. You will also get some information about the events that took place during the institute's formation and development. You can also get information about the available courses, the level of teachers and the number of students. If you want to read it here, the address is given at the bottom of the article.*

Key words: *Pedagogical, educational, competent, faculty, department, practice, doctorate.*

"ШАХРИСАБЗСКИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЙ
ИНСТИТУТ"

Аннотация. *В этой статье вы можете ознакомиться с Шахрисабзским государственным педагогическим институтом и получить полную информацию. Вы также получите информацию о событиях, происходивших в период становления и развития института. Вы также можете получить информацию о доступных курсах, уровне преподавателей и количестве студентов. Если вы хотите прочитать это здесь, адрес указан внизу статьи.*

Ключевые слова: *Педагогический, учебный, компетентный, факультет, кафедра, практика, докторантура.*

Shakhrisabz State Pedagogical Institute is located in the center of the beautiful city, located in the ancient and old- world city of "Kesh". The establishment of the institute was promoted for the first time in 2017 by the suggestions and initiatives of the director of Shakhrisabz Lyceum Ganiyev Abdukahhor Gadoyevich. The institute was approved by the population through a questionnaire. All residents accepted this decision with great joy. And in 2017, the establishment of Shakhrisabz State Pedagogical Institute named after Nizami will be considered.

For information, we can say that the educational building of Shakhrisabz Academic Lyceum with 720 seats and the Dormitory with 100 seats will serve as the basis of the material and technical base of the Institute.

The established institute was a very happy situation not only for the city of Shakhrisabz, but also for Chirakchi, Yakkabog, Kitab, Qamashi districts. The main stage for the establishment of the institute began after the visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev to Kashkadarya region on December 13-14, 2018. After these events, the President signed the law on the establishment of Shakhrisabz branches of the Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute and the Tashkent State Institute of Chemical Technology in Shakhrisabz. This signature motivated the fulfillment of the dreams of the entire people of Kashkadarya.

Educational processes in these Branches will begin in the 2019/2020 academic year, and the number of student admissions will be determined based on the quotas for admission to higher education institutions of the Republic, which are approved annually in the prescribed manner.

From September 4, 2019, the branch started its activities in the areas of Preschool Education, Primary Education and Sports Education, Foreign Language and Literature (English), Mother Language Literature, Russian Language Literature and Foreign Language Groups.

By the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. PQ-289 adopted on June 21, 2022 on measures to increase the quality of pedagogical education and training of pedagogical personnel, further development of the activities of higher educational institutions, systematic development of higher educational institutions that provide pedagogical personnel and improvement of management activities in them development of modern educational programs with the introduction of advanced foreign experiences, raising the training of highly qualified professional personnel to a new level. Also, in order to ensure the harmony of education, science and practice in the field of pedagogy, Shahrizabz State Pedagogical Institute was established on the basis of the Pedagogical Institute of Karshi State University in 2022.

★ **Today at Shahrizabz State Pedagogical Institute**

- 3 faculties

a) 15 departments

has been operating.

★ 6998 students are being educated at the institute by 202 highly qualified professors. For information, 5 of these teachers have doctorate degrees and 25 have PhD degrees.

★ Number of educational directions

1. Undergraduate full-time 16 courses

2. 11 external directions

3. Second High 11 directions

4. There are 12 fields of study at the master's level

Our available directions are:

1. Mathematics - Informatics
2. Uzbek language and literature
3. Primary education
4. Accounting and auditing
5. Chemistry
6. Preschool education
7. Information systems and technologies
8. Biology
9. Business management (by networks)

Length of study at our institute:

1. Bachelor's degree - 4 years
2. Master's degree - 2 years
3. Postgraduate course - 3 years
4. Doctoral studies - 3 years

Besides, Shahrizabz State Pedagogical Institute has a 4 + 2 system. Starting from the 2nd year, students study at the Institute for 4 days and practice in schools for 2 days.

This year, i.e. 2023, the first 4 courses will be launched as swallows.

In addition, in order to expand the Institute, in order to create more convenience for students, a 3-story modern library and a dormitory are expected to be completed in 2023.

To conclude, Come, Study, Learn and become a competent person.

Address: 10, *Shahrisabz street, Shahrisabz city, Kashkadarya.*

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